

Workshop at Damascus university
faculty of architecture
nuertingen –geislingen university
informal – settlement
march-2011

Damascus-Historical information

- The intra mores city (MORE THAN 5000 YEARS)
- The north extension(17th centuries)
- The south development axes(18th centuries)
- The northwest development axes
- The general master- plan 1936
- The general master-plan 1968 (ecochard)
- THE EAST EXTANTION (INFORMAL SETTLEMENTS)

LES CANALISATIONS ANCIENNES DE DAMAS ET LE REPERAGE DES HAMMIAMES

Fig 2

HISTORICAL INFORMATION

General development plan of Damascus 1968-master plan-

General development plan of Damascus 1968-master plan

General developing plan of Damascus master- plan (1994)

Informal housing settlements

- WHAT ARE INFORMAL HOUSING SETTLEMENTS
 - The ownership of the Land is in dispute and or is not legally registered
 - the settlement is in contravention of the master-plan land use zoning regulations
 - dwellings are constructed in contravention of building standards and regulations of the city- municipalities.

Reasons for formations informal housing areas

- Big cities attractions
- lack of the comprehensible regional strategic
- slow of update process of the cities master plans
- lack in the infrastructure of the small cities and rural areas
- shortage of the social housing strategic
- incompatible demand and supply of housing in the big cities
- increasing of internal migration

Update Google earth Site situation 2011

Law and regulations

since 1960 prevent the city municipality the upraising of illegal housing.

1964 –

1968 –

1974 –

1980 ----- 2009

General plan of Damascus showing the informal Housing Areas

General plan of Damascus showing the informal Housing Areas

The particular value and evaluation of informal settlements

- What are The particular value of the informal area
- historical value
- site importance value
- urban value
- architectural value
- social value
- environmental value
- economical value

INFRASTRUCTURE

- WATER SUPPLY
- SWERAGE
- ELECTRICIT
- SALT WATER
- EDUCATION FACILITIES
- HEALTH SERVICES

urban features of informal housing areas

- Area (relation to the city- location- surface ---)
 - density
 - urban fabric
 - public space
 - road structure
 - Transportation

Urban structure of some informal area

المقترح التنظيمي لمنطقة الطالبة - دريلة دمشق (٤) المقترح التنظيمي لمنطقة جبل ٨٦ - دمشق (٤) المقترح التنظيمي لمنطقتي ادحاديل والقابون (٤) دمشق .

دراسة واعمال الباحث

ARCHITECTURAL FEATURES

- specification of the informal housing architecture
 - house specification
 - house typology
 - house area
 - elevation
 - buildings height
 - buildings material

Social feature of the informal housing area

- Family structure
- family members education
- work possibilities
- social behavior
- economical situation

Site analysis

- Site location
- urban analysis
- Social analysis
- Architectural analysis
- Environmental analysis
- Traffic analysis

Site-City-relation

Urban structure of the site and the neighborhood

location of the informal housing part

location and shape of the informal housing part

Urban structure of the informal housing part

location and area surface of the informal housing part

Solutions and proposals

- The solutions can be in three levels
- Municipality solutions and proposals(master-plan)
- Strategic solutions
- Procedural solutions
 - demolishing
 - rehabilitation
 - upgrading
 - integrating
- Other proposal solutions

Conclusion

- Should the informal context considered as urban consistency, of the city
- Can we act changing in the informal context according to the benefit of the city
- Do the benefit of the social needs take the priority in this process
- Do the inhabitation demands take place in this conflict process
- Do other needs ,social ,environmental, infrastructural, economical take the priority in this confrontation
- Do we ask our self such as questions before start..... acting, demolishing, evacuating, etc.....